

Management by Sufficient Economy Philosophy for Hospitality Business in Samut Songkram

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Abstract : The objectives of this research are to know the management form of Samut Songkram lodging entrepreneurs with sufficient economy framework, to know the threat that affect this business and drawing the fit model for this province in order to sustain their business with Samut Songkram style. What will happen if they do not use this philosophy? Will they have a cash short fall? The data and information are collected by informal discussion with 8 managers and 400 questionnaires. We will use a mix of methods both qualitative research and quantitative research for our study. Bent Flyvbjerg's phronesis is utilized for this analysis. Our research will prove that sufficient economy can help small and medium business firms solve their problems. We think that the results of our research will be a financial model to solve many problems of the entrepreneurs and this way will use to practice in other areas of our country.

Keywords : Samut Songkram, hospitality business, sufficient economy philosophy, style

Conference Title : ICMBSS 2014 : International Conference on Management, Business and Social Sciences

Conference Location : London, United Kingdom

Conference Dates : January 20-21, 2014